

Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 19

The work is also available at author's site:

<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=9812>

Inder J. Taneja¹

Abstract

During past years author worked with **borderedmagic squares** of even number blocks. These are based on equal sums magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10, etc. This type of work is an extension of classical bordered magic squares. In case of multiples of 4, the extension is made for **pandiagonal** magic squares [23]. For multiples of order 6 refer Taneja [24]. Recently, author worked on odd number multiples from 3 to 17. These are based on different sums of magic squares of orders 3 to 15 [29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36]. This work is for multiples of 19. We have worked with 42 different types of magic squares of order 19. Total work is up to order 133, but due to space problems the examples given here are only for orders 19 and 57. Higher order examples can be seen in **Excel files** attached with the work.

¹Formerly, Professor of Mathematics, Federal University of Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil (1978-2012).
Also worked at Delhi University, India (1976-1978).
E-mail: ijjtaneja@gmail.com;
Web-sites: <http://inderjtaneja.com>; <http://numbers-magic.com>;
Twitter: @IJTANEJA; **Instagram:** @crazynumbers.

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1 Introduction

During past years author [2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8] worked with **block-wise** magic squares from orders 12 to 47. Author [9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14] also worked with **bordered** magic squares. The study on **bordered** magic squares is extended to **block-bordered** magic squares [15, 16, 17]. This is specially done for the magic squares of orders p and $2p$, where p is a prime number. This study is still extended to **block-wise bordered** magic squares [18, 19, 20, 21]. Some connection with Pythagorean triples and area-representations are also made [23, 24, 25, 26, 27]. The main property of **bordered** magic squares is that if we remove external borders, still we get **sub-bordered** magic squares, i.e., each layer in itself lead us to magic squares. In many cases, the properties of **bordered** magic square are separated by **even** and **odd** orders magic squares. In many cases, we get good properties for the **even** order **bordered** magic squares. In some cases, we have to use fractional numbers to reach minimum perfect square sum of entries. For more study on **bordered** magic squares refer H. White’s web-site [1].

The idea of bordered magic squares is already discussed by H. White’s web-site [1] where the borders are of **single digits**. Borders multiples of even numbers starting from order 4 are done extensively by author [23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28].

1.1 Summary of Bordered Magic Squares

1.1.1 Odd Numbers Multiples

- **Single Digit:** Bordered magic squares based on single digit [9, 10, 1].
- **Three Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 3 [29].
- **Five Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 5 [30].
- **Seven Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 7 [31].
- **Nine Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 9 [32]
- **Eleven Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 11 [33]
- **Thirteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 13 [34]
- **Fifteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 15 [35]
- **Seventeen Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 17 [36]
- **Nineteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 19 [37] (This work)

1.1.2 Even Numbers Multiples

- **Two Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic rectangles multiples of 2 [77, 78, 66, 67, 67, 68].
- **Four Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 4 [23].
- **Six Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 6 [24].
- **Eight Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 8 [25].
- **Ten Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 10 [26].
- **Twelve Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 12 [27].

- **Fourteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 14 [28].

The work on even number multiples is with equal sums blocks of magic squares. The work on odd number multiples is with different sum magic squares.

This work is for bordered magic squares multiples of 19. Here are working with 42 different types of magic square of order 19. The procedure, how these bordered magic squares are obtained is also given. Higher orders examples can be seen in **Excel files** attached with this work.

2 Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 19

Let's consider following 42 magic squares of order 19.

5	mgc	3211	3730	2457	3840	2870	3816	3294	2995	3028	4167	3544	3629	3050	4360	3041	3979	3259	3632	3439
41	338	54	345	331	44	307	60	59	356	316	325	39	62	25	328	47	29	333	3439	
321	24	308	17	31	318	55	302	303	6	46	37	323	300	337	34	315	43	319	3439	
7	355	165	168	148	150	149	290	293	273	275	274	115	118	98	100	99	330	32	3439	
295	67	145	155	160	153	167	270	280	285	278	292	95	105	110	103	117	305	57	3439	
53	309	146	154	156	158	166	271	279	281	283	291	96	104	106	108	116	12	350	3439	
351	11	161	159	152	157	151	286	284	277	282	276	111	109	102	107	101	64	298	3439	
347	15	163	144	164	162	147	288	269	289	287	272	113	94	114	112	97	13	349	3439	
30	332	140	143	123	125	124	190	193	173	175	174	240	243	223	225	224	314	48	3439	
20	342	120	130	135	128	142	170	180	185	178	192	220	230	235	228	242	35	327	3439	
360	2	121	129	131	133	141	171	179	181	183	191	221	229	231	233	241	324	38	3439	
51	311	136	134	127	132	126	186	184	177	182	176	236	234	227	232	226	296	66	3439	
63	299	138	119	139	137	122	188	169	189	187	172	238	219	239	237	222	3	359	3439	
49	313	265	268	248	250	249	90	93	73	75	74	215	218	198	200	199	294	68	3439	
352	10	245	255	260	253	267	70	80	85	78	92	195	205	210	203	217	317	45	3439	
52	310	246	254	256	258	266	71	79	81	83	91	196	204	206	208	216	322	40	3439	
1	361	261	259	252	257	251	86	84	77	82	76	211	209	202	207	201	326	36	3439	
354	8	263	244	264	262	247	88	69	89	87	72	213	194	214	212	197	50	312	3439	
353	9	5	65	19	14	18	304	334	306	26	320	340	329	16	341	335	301	4	3439	
339	23	357	297	343	348	344	58	28	56	336	42	22	33	346	21	27	61	358	3439	
3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439

6	mgc	3335	3643	2603	3942	3580	3829	3603	2848	3168	4113	3669	3342	2572	3990	2873	4235	2720	3837	3439
41	338	54	345	331	44	307	60	59	356	316	325	39	62	25	328	47	29	333	3439	
321	24	308	17	31	318	55	302	303	6	46	37	323	300	337	34	315	43	319	3439	
7	355	273	280	117	114	268	264	256	104	100	75	118	281	103	102	260	330	32	3439	
295	67	89	82	245	248	94	98	106	258	262	287	244	81	259	112	250	305	57	3439	
53	309	269	93	130	153	236	134	148	230	227	231	140	137	225	288	74	12	350	3439	
351	11	284	78	232	209	126	228	214	132	135	131	222	221	141	113	249	64	298	3439	
347	15	79	283	220	142	189	166	176	169	205	188	174	212	150	116	246	13	349	3439	
30	332	109	253	237	125	196	204	163	164	172	180	188	138	224	91	271	314	48	3439	
20	342	261	101	147	215	179	187	195	203	162	170	171	238	124	243	119	35	327	3439	
360	2	265	97	127	235	169	177	178	186	194	202	161	218	144	276	86	324	38	3439	
51	311	85	277	136	226	201	160	168	176	184	185	193	121	241	290	72	296	66	3439	
63	299	71	291	211	151	191	192	200	159	167	175	183	128	234	69	293	3	359	3439	
49	313	76	286	155	207	174	182	190	198	199	158	166	216	146	279	83	294	68	3439	
352	10	263	99	240	122	239	145	154	143	223	149	133	233	210	96	266	317	45	3439	
52	310	87	275	156	206	123	217	208	219	139	213	229	129	152	278	84	322	40	3439	
1	361	257	105	120	267	107	88	282	111	254	110	73	272	92	292	285	326	36	3439	
354	8	247	115	242	95	255	274	80	251	108	252	289	90	270	70	77	50	312	3439	
353	9	5	65	19	14	18	304	334	306	26	320	340	329	16	341	335	301	4	3439	
339	23	357	297	343	348	344	58	28	56	336	42	22	33	346	21	27	61	358	3439	
3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439

7	mgc	3399	3576	2581	4014	3536	3824	3603	2848	3168	4113	3669	3342	2540	4012	2887	4193	2734	3863	3439
41	338	54	345	331	44	307	60	59	356	316	325	39	62	25	328	47	29	333	3439	
321	24	308	17	31	318	55	302	303	6	46	37	323	300	337	34	315	43	319	3439	
7	355	273	280	117	114	268	264	256	104	100	75	118	281	103	102	260	330	32	3439	
295	67	89	82	245	248	94	98	106	258	262	287	244	81	259	112	250	305	57	3439	
53	309	269	93	130	153	236	134	148	230	227	231	140	137	225	288	74	12	350	3439	
351	11	284	78	232	209	126	228	214	132	135	131	222	221	141	113	249	64	298	3439	
347	15	79	283	220	142	157	165	173	181	189	197	205	212	150	116	246	13	349	3439	
30	332	109	253	237	125	196	204	163	164	172	180	188	138	224	91	271	314	48	3439	
20	342	261	101	147	215	179	187	195	203	162	170	171	238	124	243	119	35	327	3439	
360	2	265	97	127	235	169	177	178	186	194	202	161	218	144	276	86	324	38	3439	
51	311	85	277	136	226	201	160	168	176	184	185	193	121	241	290	72	296	66	3439	
63	299	71	291	211	151	191	192	200	159	167	175	183	128	234	69	293	3	359	3439	
49	313	76	286	155	207	174	182	190	198	199	158	166	216	146	279	83	294	68	3439	
352	10	263	99	240	122	239	145	154	143	223	149	133	233	210	96	266	317	45	3439	
52	310	87	275	156	206	123	217	208	219	139	213	229	129	152	278	84	322	40	3439	
1	361	257	105	120	267	107	88	282	111	254	110	73	272	92	292	285	326	36	3439	
354	8	247	115	242	95	255	274	80	251	108	252	289	90	270	70	77	50	312	3439	
353	9	5	65	19	14	18	304	334	306	26	320	340	329	16	341	335	301	4	3439	
339	23	357	297	343	348	344	58	28	56	336	42	22	33	346	21	27	61	358	3439	
3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439

8	mgc	3370	3769	2387	4148	3582	3967	3332	2933	3239	4072	3547	3422	2640	3962	2868	4175	2860	3629	3439
41	338	54	345	331	44	307	60	59	356	316	325	39	62							

9	mgc	3370	3769	2387	4148	3582	3967	3332	2933	3230	4065	3555	3432	2640	3991	2840	4167	2865	3629	3439	
		41	338	54	345	331	44	307	60	59	356	316	325	39	62	25	328	47	29	333	3439
		321	24	308	17	31	318	55	302	303	6	46	37	323	300	337	34	315	43	319	3439
		7	355	273	280	117	114	268	264	256	104	100	75	118	281	103	102	260	330	32	3439
		295	67	89	82	245	248	94	98	106	258	262	287	244	81	259	112	250	305	57	3439
		53	309	269	93	169	175	181	187	193	194	168	147	215	139	223	288	74	12	350	3439
		351	11	284	78	186	192	173	174	180	201	161	156	206	230	132	113	249	64	298	3439
		347	15	79	283	178	179	185	191	172	198	164	152	210	133	229	116	246	13	349	3439
		30	332	109	253	190	171	177	183	184	195	167	154	208	240	122	91	271	314	48	3439
		20	342	261	101	182	188	189	170	176	159	203	217	145	135	227	243	119	35	327	3439
		360	2	265	97	196	160	197	200	158	157	199	214	148	131	231	276	86	324	38	3439
		51	311	85	277	166	202	165	162	204	163	205	153	209	235	127	290	72	296	66	3439
		63	299	71	291	218	219	155	149	150	151	221	220	146	236	126	69	293	3	359	3439
		49	313	76	286	144	143	207	213	212	211	141	216	142	140	222	279	83	294	68	3439
		352	10	263	99	232	124	226	123	121	225	129	228	125	234	224	96	266	317	45	3439
		52	310	87	275	130	238	136	239	241	137	233	134	237	138	128	278	84	322	40	3439
		1	361	257	105	120	267	107	88	282	111	254	110	73	272	92	292	285	326	36	3439
		354	8	247	115	242	95	255	274	80	251	108	252	289	90	270	70	77	50	312	3439
		353	9	5	65	19	14	18	304	334	306	26	320	340	329	16	341	335	301	4	3439
		339	23	357	297	343	348	344	58	28	56	336	42	22	33	346	21	27	61	358	3439
		3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439

10	mgc	3294	3789	2388	4148	3582	3967	3332	2933	3218	4065	3560	3403	2661	3966	2868	4172	2925	3631	3439	
		41	338	54	345	331	44	307	60	59	356	316	325	39	62	25	328	47	29	333	3439
		321	24	308	17	31	318	55	302	303	6	46	37	323	300	337	34	315	43	319	3439
		7	355	273	280	117	114	268	264	256	104	100	75	118	281	103	102	260	330	32	3439
		295	67	89	82	245	248	94	98	106	258	262	287	244	81	259	112	250	305	57	3439
		53	309	269	93	157	165	173	181	189	197	205	154	208	139	223	288	74	12	350	3439
		351	11	284	78	196	204	163	164	172	180	188	217	145	230	132	113	249	64	298	3439
		347	15	79	283	179	187	195	203	162	170	171	156	206	133	229	116	246	13	349	3439
		30	332	109	253	169	177	178	186	194	202	161	147	215	240	122	91	271	314	48	3439
		20	342	261	101	201	160	168	176	184	185	193	152	210	135	227	243	119	35	327	3439
		360	2	265	97	191	192	200	159	167	175	183	214	148	131	231	276	86	324	38	3439
		51	311	85	277	174	182	190	198	199	158	166	153	209	235	127	290	72	296	66	3439
		63	299	71	291	218	219	155	151	149	150	221	220	146	236	126	69	293	3	359	3439
		49	313	76	286	144	143	207	211	213	212	141	216	142	140	222	279	83	294	68	3439
		352	10	263	99	226	124	232	123	121	225	129	228	125	234	224	96	266	317	45	3439
		52	310	87	275	136	238	130	239	241	137	233	134	237	138	128	278	84	322	40	3439
		1	361	257	105	120	267	107	88	282	111	254	110	73	272	92	292	285	326	36	3439
		354	8	247	115	242	95	255	274	80	251	108	252	289	90	270	70	77	50	312	3439
		353	9	5	65	19	14	18	304	334	306	26	320	340	329	16	341	335	301	4	3439
		339	23	357	297	343	348	344	58	28	56	336	42	22	33	346	21	27	61	358	3439
		3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439

11	mgc	3209	3856	2364	4127	3660	3917	3337	2934	3223	4090	3541	3428	2641	3945	2910	4101	2860	3759	3439	
		41	338	54	345	331	44	307	60	59	356	316	325	39	62	25	328	47	29	333	3439
		321	24	308	17	31	318	55	302	303	6	46	37	323	300	337	34	315	43	319	3439
		7	355	273	280	117	114	268	264	256	104	100	75	118	281	103	102	260	330	32	3439
		295	67	89	82	245	248	94	98	106	258	262	287	244	81	259	112	250	305	57	3439
		53	309	269	93	162	211	170	167	204	172	178	146	219	140	222	288	74	12	350	3439
		351	11	284	78	175	161	207	168	163	212	218	183	142	236	126	113	249	64	298	3439
		347	15	79	283	206	171	166	208	176	159	147	214	182	133	229	116	246	13	349	3439
		30	332	109	253	180	148	215	185	141	217	160	209	174	235	127	91	271	314	48	3439
		20	342	261	101	220	179	144	213	181	149	173	165	205	135	227	243	119	35	327	3439
		360	2	265	97	143	216	184	145	221	177	210	169	164	131	231	276	86	324	38	3439
		51	311	85	277	198	193	152	203	186	154	196	191	156	240	122	290	72	296	66	3439
		63	299	71	291	157	197	189	150	199	194	155	201	187	230	132	69	293	3	359	3439
		49	313	76	286	188	153	202	190	158	195	192	151	200	139	223	279	83	294	68	3439
		352	10	263	99	232	124	129	123	121	225	226	228	125	234	224	96	266	317	45	3439
		52	310	87	275	130	238	233	239	241	137	136	134	237	138	128	278	84	322	40	3439
		1	361	257	105	120	267	107	88	282	111	254	110	73	272	92	292	285	326	36	3439
		354	8	247	115	242	95	255	274	80	251	108	252	289	90	270	70	77	50	312	3439
		353	9	5	65	19	14	18	304	334	306	26	320	340	329	16	341	335	301	4	3439
		339	23	357	297	343	348	344	58	28	56	336	42	22	33	346	21	27	61	358	3439
		3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439

12	mgc	3315	3712	2495	4442	2951	3848	3719	3123	2723	4346	3205	3826	2831	3783	2820	3966	3214	3583	3439	
		41	338	54	345	331	44	307	60	59	356	316	325	39	62	25	328	47	29	333	3439
		321	24	308	17	31	318	55	302	303	6	46	37	323	300	337	34	315	43	319	3439
		7	355	178	185	180	193	169	195	167	212	150	135	227	120	242	77	285	330	32	3439
		295	67	183	181	179	192	170	201	161	210	152	132	230	109	253	71	291	305	57	3439
		53	309	182	177	184	172	190													

13	mgc	3315	3712	2495	4442	2942	3841	3727	3127	2723	4361	3213	3818	2820	3783	2820	3966	3214	3583	3439
41	338	54	345	331	44	307	60	59	356	316	325	39	62	25	328	47	29	333	3439	
321	24	308	17	31	318	55	302	303	6	46	37	323	300	337	34	315	43	319	3439	
7	355	169	175	181	187	193	195	167	212	150	135	227	120	242	77	285	330	32	3439	
295	67	186	192	173	174	180	201	161	210	152	132	230	109	253	71	291	305	57	3439	
53	309	178	179	185	191	172	162	200	147	215	235	127	108	254	76	286	12	350	3439	
351	11	190	171	177	183	184	157	205	146	216	236	126	252	110	273	89	64	298	3439	
347	15	182	188	189	170	176	160	202	208	154	131	231	118	244	75	287	13	349	3439	
30	332	158	159	199	196	197	194	164	206	156	130	232	259	103	269	93	314	48	3439	
20	342	204	203	163	166	165	198	168	214	148	239	123	263	99	281	81	35	327	3439	
360	2	217	221	155	151	149	219	153	144	220	240	122	258	104	274	88	324	38	3439	
51	311	145	141	207	211	213	143	209	142	218	139	223	113	249	69	293	296	66	3439	
63	299	138	128	137	238	233	140	237	134	136	241	229	119	243	271	91	3	359	3439	
49	313	224	234	225	124	129	222	125	228	226	133	121	264	98	74	288	294	68	3439	
352	10	248	102	250	251	247	100	255	101	245	106	246	105	97	283	79	317	45	3439	
52	310	114	260	112	111	115	262	107	261	117	256	116	265	257	78	284	322	40	3439	
1	361	292	289	279	94	85	280	87	92	282	290	90	86	95	278	96	326	36	3439	
354	8	70	73	83	268	277	82	275	270	80	72	272	276	267	266	84	50	312	3439	
353	9	5	65	19	14	18	304	334	306	26	320	340	329	16	341	335	301	4	3439	
339	23	357	297	343	348	344	58	28	56	336	42	22	33	346	21	27	61	358	3439	
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14	mgc	3315	3712	2495	4442	2930	3841	3732	3098	2744	4373	3205	3849	2834	3766	2826	3945	3212	3583	3439
41	338	54	345	331	44	307	60	59	356	316	325	39	62	25	328	47	29	333	3439	
321	24	308	17	31	318	55	302	303	6	46	37	323	300	337	34	315	43	319	3439	
7	355	157	165	173	181	189	197	205	212	150	135	227	120	242	77	285	330	32	3439	
295	67	196	204	163	164	172	180	188	210	152	132	230	109	253	71	291	305	57	3439	
53	309	179	187	195	203	162	170	171	147	215	235	127	108	254	76	286	12	350	3439	
351	11	169	177	178	186	194	202	161	146	216	236	126	252	110	273	89	64	298	3439	
347	15	201	160	168	176	184	185	193	208	154	131	231	118	244	75	287	13	349	3439	
30	332	191	192	200	159	167	175	183	206	156	130	232	259	103	269	93	314	48	3439	
20	342	174	182	190	198	199	158	166	214	148	239	123	263	99	281	81	35	327	3439	
360	2	217	221	155	151	149	219	153	144	220	240	122	258	104	274	88	324	38	3439	
51	311	145	141	207	211	213	143	209	142	218	139	223	113	249	69	293	296	66	3439	
63	299	138	128	137	238	233	140	237	134	136	241	229	119	243	271	91	3	359	3439	
49	313	224	234	225	124	129	222	125	228	226	133	121	264	98	74	288	294	68	3439	
352	10	248	102	250	251	247	100	255	101	245	106	246	105	97	283	79	317	45	3439	
52	310	114	260	112	111	115	262	107	261	117	256	116	265	257	78	284	322	40	3439	
1	361	292	289	279	94	85	280	87	92	282	290	90	86	95	278	96	326	36	3439	
354	8	70	73	83	268	277	82	275	270	80	72	272	276	267	266	84	50	312	3439	
353	9	5	65	19	14	18	304	334	306	26	320	340	329	16	341	335	301	4	3439	
339	23	357	297	343	348	344	58	28	56	336	42	22	33	346	21	27	61	358	3439	
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15	mgc	3305	3698	2482	4455	2941	3860	3713	3123	2724	4352	3246	3722	2831	3891	2831	3888	3188	3652	3439
41	338	54	345	331	44	307	60	59	356	316	325	39	62	25	328	47	29	333	3439	
321	24	308	17	31	318	55	302	303	6	46	37	323	300	337	34	315	43	319	3439	
7	355	162	211	170	167	204	172	178	146	219	135	227	108	254	78	284	330	32	3439	
295	67	175	161	207	168	163	212	218	183	142	132	230	109	253	71	291	305	57	3439	
53	309	206	171	166	208	176	159	147	214	182	235	127	120	242	76	286	12	350	3439	
351	11	180	148	215	185	141	217	160	209	174	236	126	252	110	273	89	64	298	3439	
347	15	220	179	144	213	181	149	173	165	205	139	223	118	244	75	287	13	349	3439	
30	332	143	216	184	145	221	177	210	169	164	130	232	259	103	269	93	314	48	3439	
20	342	198	193	152	203	186	154	196	191	156	239	123	263	99	281	81	35	327	3439	
360	2	157	197	189	150	199	194	155	201	187	240	122	258	104	274	88	324	38	3439	
51	311	188	153	202	190	158	195	192	151	200	131	231	113	249	69	293	296	66	3439	
63	299	138	140	137	238	237	128	233	134	136	241	229	119	243	271	91	3	359	3439	
49	313	224	222	225	124	125	234	129	228	226	133	121	264	98	74	288	294	68	3439	
352	10	248	102	255	245	247	100	250	101	251	106	246	105	97	283	79	317	45	3439	
52	310	114	260	107	117	115	262	112	261	111	256	116	265	257	77	285	322	40	3439	
1	361	292	289	279	94	85	280	87	92	282	290	90	86	95	278	96	326	36	3439	
354	8	70	73	83	268	277	82	275	270	80	72	272	276	267	266	84	50	312	3439	
353	9	5	65	19	14	18	304	334	306	26	320	340	329	16	341	335	301	4	3439	
339	23	357	297	343	348	344	58	28	56	336	42	22	33	346	21	27	61	358	3439	
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16	mgc	3437	3647	2715	3915	3083	4151	3637	3257	2641	4261	3433	3341	3038	4067	2857	3749	3214	3459	3439
41	338	54	345	331	44	307	60	59	356	316	325	39								

17	mgc	3413	3667	2715	3915	3083	4151	3637	3257	2641	4261	3433	3341	3032	4077	2855	3753	3214	3457	3439
41	338	54	345	331	44	307	60	59	356	316	325	39	62	25	328	47	29	333	3439	
321	24	308	17	31	318	55	302	303	6	46	37	323	300	337	34	315	43	319	3439	
7	355	117	122	260	228	108	256	99	105	230	239	227	115	247	78	284	330	32	3439	
295	67	245	240	102	134	254	106	263	257	132	123	135	232	130	269	93	305	57	3439	
53	309	140	222	211	215	165	143	150	217	166	204	158	243	119	76	286	12	350	3439	
351	11	249	113	151	147	197	219	212	145	196	200	162	223	139	273	89	64	298	3439	
347	15	262	100	141	221	172	188	183	180	182	149	213	235	127	75	287	13	349	3439	
30	332	242	120	153	209	190	174	179	193	169	142	220	125	237	71	291	314	48	3439	
20	342	109	253	208	154	184	178	181	170	192	195	167	129	233	281	81	35	327	3439	
360	2	98	264	205	157	186	176	177	191	175	161	201	101	261	274	88	324	38	3439	
51	311	121	241	152	210	173	189	185	171	187	216	146	114	248	69	293	296	66	3439	
63	299	112	250	202	160	194	163	159	155	164	218	214	238	124	271	91	3	359	3439	
49	313	265	97	206	156	168	199	203	207	198	144	148	236	126	74	288	294	68	3439	
352	10	255	107	258	110	225	251	259	131	116	136	244	133	128	77	285	317	45	3439	
52	310	138	224	104	252	137	111	103	231	246	226	118	229	234	283	79	322	40	3439	
1	361	95	85	279	94	289	280	87	92	282	290	90	86	292	278	96	326	36	3439	
354	8	267	277	83	268	73	82	275	270	80	72	272	276	70	266	84	50	312	3439	
353	9	5	65	19	14	18	304	334	306	26	320	340	329	16	341	335	301	4	3439	
339	23	357	297	343	348	344	58	28	56	336	42	22	33	346	21	27	61	358	3439	
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18	mgc	3374	3698	2649	3903	3051	4215	3637	3257	2592	4281	3517	3352	2980	3991	2985	3647	3214	3559	3439
41	338	54	345	331	44	307	60	59	356	316	325	39	62	25	328	47	29	333	3439	
321	24	308	17	31	318	55	302	303	6	46	37	323	300	337	34	315	43	319	3439	
7	355	117	122	260	228	108	256	99	105	230	239	227	115	247	78	284	330	32	3439	
295	67	245	240	102	134	254	106	263	257	132	123	135	232	130	269	93	305	57	3439	
53	309	140	222	162	211	170	167	204	172	160	209	174	243	119	76	286	12	350	3439	
351	11	249	113	175	161	207	168	163	212	173	165	205	223	139	273	89	64	298	3439	
347	15	262	100	206	171	166	208	176	159	210	169	164	235	127	75	287	13	349	3439	
30	332	242	120	180	148	215	185	141	217	178	146	219	125	237	71	291	314	48	3439	
20	342	109	253	220	179	144	213	181	149	218	183	142	129	233	269	93	35	327	3439	
360	2	98	264	143	216	184	145	221	177	147	214	182	101	261	274	88	324	38	3439	
51	311	121	241	198	193	152	203	186	154	196	191	156	114	248	69	293	296	66	3439	
63	299	112	250	157	197	189	150	199	194	155	201	187	238	124	271	91	3	359	3439	
49	313	265	97	188	153	202	190	158	195	192	151	200	236	126	74	288	294	68	3439	
352	10	255	107	259	110	225	251	258	131	116	136	244	133	128	77	285	317	45	3439	
52	310	138	224	103	252	137	111	104	231	246	226	118	229	234	283	79	322	40	3439	
1	361	95	85	279	94	289	280	87	92	282	290	90	86	292	278	96	326	36	3439	
354	8	267	277	83	268	73	82	275	270	80	72	272	276	70	266	84	50	312	3439	
353	9	5	65	19	14	18	304	334	306	26	320	340	329	16	341	335	301	4	3439	
339	23	357	297	343	348	344	58	28	56	336	42	22	33	346	21	27	61	358	3439	
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19	mgc	3438	3628	2577	3998	3087	4159	3637	3257	2608	4263	3523	3333	2979	4017	2961	3616	3250	3571	3439
41	338	54	345	331	44	307	60	59	356	316	325	39	62	25	328	47	29	333	3439	
321	24	308	17	31	318	55	302	303	6	46	37	323	300	337	34	315	43	319	3439	
7	355	117	122	260	228	108	256	99	105	230	239	227	115	247	78	284	330	32	3439	
295	67	245	240	102	134	254	106	263	257	132	123	135	232	130	269	93	305	57	3439	
53	309	140	222	178	183	182	174	188	163	199	207	155	243	119	76	286	12	350	3439	
351	11	249	113	185	181	177	175	187	198	164	145	217	223	139	273	89	64	298	3439	
347	15	262	100	180	179	184	192	170	159	203	144	218	235	127	75	287	13	349	3439	
30	332	242	120	176	172	173	193	191	158	204	212	150	125	237	71	291	314	48	3439	
20	342	109	253	186	190	189	171	169	195	167	209	153	129	233	281	81	35	327	3439	
360	2	98	264	201	157	160	196	197	194	162	149	213	101	261	274	88	324	38	3439	
51	311	121	241	161	205	202	166	165	200	168	143	219	114	248	69	293	296	66	3439	
63	299	112	250	141	216	211	147	208	210	142	206	148	238	124	271	91	3	359	3439	
49	313	265	97	221	146	151	215	154	152	220	214	156	236	126	74	288	294	68	3439	
352	10	255	107	258	110	225	251	259	131	116	136	244	133	128	77	285	317	45	3439	
52	310	138	224	104	252	137	111	103	231	246	226	118	229	234	283	79	322	40	3439	
1	361	95	85	279	94	289	280	87	92	282	290	90	86	292	278	96	326	36	3439	
354	8	267	277	83	268	73	82	275	270	80	72	272	276	70	266	84	50	312	3439	
353	9	5	65	19	14	18	304	334	306	26	320	340	329	16	341	335	301	4	3439	
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20	mgc	3438	3628	2577	3998	3087	4159	3637	3257	2599	4256	3531	3356	2979	4011	2953	3608	3257	3571	3439
41	338	54	345	331	44	307	60	59	356	316	325	39								

21	mgc	3466	3689	2513	3999	3087	4159	3646	3248	2587	4256	3522	3341	3000	4012	2961	3676	3228	3512	3439
41	338	54	345	331	44	307	60	59	356	316	325	39	62	25	328	47	29	333	3439	
321	24	308	17	31	318	55	302	303	6	46	37	323	300	337	34	315	43	319	3439	
7	355	117	122	260	228	108	256	99	105	230	239	227	115	247	69	293	330	32	3439	
295	67	245	240	102	134	254	106	263	257	132	123	135	232	130	283	79	305	57	3439	
53	309	140	222	157	165	173	181	189	197	205	207	155	243	119	76	286	12	350	3439	
351	11	249	113	196	204	163	164	172	180	188	145	217	223	139	273	89	64	298	3439	
347	15	262	100	179	187	195	203	162	170	171	144	218	235	127	75	287	13	349	3439	
30	332	242	120	169	177	178	186	194	202	161	149	213	125	237	71	291	314	48	3439	
20	342	109	253	201	160	168	176	184	185	193	209	153	129	233	281	81	35	327	3439	
360	2	98	264	191	192	200	159	167	175	183	212	150	101	261	274	88	324	38	3439	
51	311	121	241	174	182	190	198	199	158	166	143	219	114	248	78	284	296	66	3439	
63	299	112	250	141	216	211	147	208	210	142	206	148	238	124	271	91	3	359	3439	
49	313	265	97	221	146	151	215	154	152	220	214	156	236	126	74	288	294	68	3439	
352	10	255	107	259	110	225	251	258	131	116	136	244	133	128	77	285	317	45	3439	
52	310	138	224	103	252	137	111	104	231	246	226	118	229	234	269	93	322	40	3439	
1	361	95	85	279	94	289	280	87	92	282	290	90	86	292	278	96	326	36	3439	
354	8	267	277	83	268	73	82	275	270	80	72	272	276	70	266	84	50	312	3439	
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22	mgc	3664	2699	3704	3092	3761	2871	4442	3011	3756	3507	3652	3083	2677	4074	3114	3597	3439	3759	3439
303	82	40	61	38	68	272	295	298	315	278	299	37	288	41	73	289	354	8	3439	
59	280	322	301	324	294	90	67	64	47	84	63	325	74	321	43	319	359	3	3439	
86	276	236	111	138	227	229	117	235	238	103	97	260	128	234	57	305	353	9	3439	
54	308	126	251	224	135	133	245	127	124	259	265	102	129	233	268	94	360	2	3439	
309	53	242	120	146	157	213	203	200	204	144	215	147	226	136	275	87	355	7	3439	
79	283	119	243	216	205	149	159	162	158	218	196	166	104	258	60	302	347	15	3439	
69	293	225	137	210	152	189	170	184	186	176	201	161	108	254	71	291	351	11	3439	
55	307	131	231	206	156	173	192	178	188	174	163	199	101	261	48	314	27	335	3439	
313	49	132	230	165	197	175	187	181	169	193	142	220	253	109	65	297	348	14	3439	
323	39	123	239	217	145	185	177	180	172	191	143	219	222	140	267	95	357	5	3439	
304	58	118	244	168	194	183	179	182	190	171	207	155	223	139	311	51	28	334	3439	
284	78	252	110	141	221	151	212	154	148	195	209	198	250	112	317	45	19	343	3439	
70	292	122	240	160	202	211	150	208	214	167	153	164	247	115	273	89	24	338	3439	
83	279	264	98	228	106	105	113	232	237	248	100	255	121	246	269	93	34	328	3439	
76	286	263	99	134	256	257	249	130	125	114	262	107	241	116	318	44	30	332	3439	
290	72	96	92	271	282	300	46	50	56	274	52	277	281	285	66	287	23	339	3439	
320	42	266	270	91	80	62	316	312	306	88	310	85	81	77	296	75	18	344	3439	
356	361	341	33	29	16	25	36	22	26	32	361	349	358	31	350	352	35	345	3439	
6	1	21	329	333	346	337	326	340	336	330	20	13	4	331	12	10	17	327	3439	
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23	mgc	3965	2920	3385	3122	3731	2913	4440	3012	3777	3525	3872	2815	2685	4025	3157	3601	3439	3518	3439
303	82	40	61	38	68	272	295	298	315	278	299	37	288	41	73	289	24	338	3439	
59	280	322	301	324	294	90	67	64	47	84	63	325	74	321	43	319	354	8	3439	
86	276	236	111	138	227	229	117	235	238	103	97	260	128	234	57	297	353	9	3439	
54	308	126	251	224	135	133	245	127	124	259	265	102	129	233	57	305	360	2	3439	
309	53	242	120	167	204	172	180	148	215	160	209	174	226	136	275	87	355	7	3439	
79	283	119	243	168	163	212	220	179	144	173	165	205	104	258	267	95	359	3	3439	
69	293	225	137	208	176	159	143	216	184	210	169	164	108	254	71	291	351	11	3439	
55	307	131	231	198	193	152	185	141	217	178	146	219	101	261	48	314	27	335	3439	
313	49	132	230	157	197	189	213	181	149	218	183	142	253	109	60	302	347	15	3439	
323	39	123	239	188	153	202	145	221	177	147	214	182	222	140	268	94	357	5	3439	
304	58	118	244	162	211	170	203	186	154	196	191	156	223	139	311	51	28	334	3439	
284	78	252	110	175	161	207	150	199	194	155	201	187	250	112	317	45	19	343	3439	
70	292	122	240	206	171	166	190	158	195	192	151	200	247	115	273	89	348	14	3439	
83	279	264	98	228	106	105	113	232	237	248	100	255	121	246	269	93	34	328	3439	
76	286	263	99	134	256	257	249	130	125	114	262	107	241	116	318	44	30	332	3439	
290	72	96	92	271	282	300	46	50	56	274	52	277	281	285	66	287	23	339	3439	
320	42	266	270	91	80	62	316	312	306	88	310	85	81	77	296	75	18	344	3439	
356	342	341	33	29	16	25	36	22	26	32	361	349	358	31	350	352	35	345	3439	
6	20	21	329	333	346	337	326	340	336	330	1	13	4	331	12	10	17	327	3439	
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24	mgc	4113	3187	3329	3392	3242	3154	3753	3333	3108	3638	3758	3535	2614	4108	3436	3613	3439	3150	3439
273	280	117	114	268	264	256	104	100	75	118	281	103	102	260	294	68	348	14	3439	
89	82	245	248	94	98	106	258	262	287	244	81	259	112	250	307	55	360	2	3439	
269	93	130	153	236	134	148	230	227	231	140	137	225	288	74	40	322	353	9	3439	
284	78	232	209	126	228	214	132	135	131	222	221	141	116	246	50	312	354	8	3439	
79	283	220	142	189	166	176	169	205	188	174	212	150	113	249	306	56	359	3	3439	
109	253	237	125	173	196	186	193	157	161	201	238	124	91	271	303	59	355	7	3439	
261	101	147	215	170	192	184	177	182	158	204	138	224	243	119	41	321	351	11	3439	
265	97	127	235	195	167	179	181	183	198	164	218	144	276	86	297	65	27	335	3439	
85																				

25	mgc	4068	3182	3329	3397	3237	3149	3759	3331	3070	3667	3772	3493	2628	4134	3436	3610	3439	3201	3439
273	280	117	114	268	264	256	104	100	75	118	281	103	102	260	301	61	347	15	3439	
89	82	245	248	94	98	106	258	262	287	244	81	259	112	250	307	55	355	7	3439	
269	93	130	153	236	134	148	230	227	231	140	137	225	288	74	40	322	353	9	3439	
284	78	232	209	126	228	214	132	135	131	222	221	141	116	246	51	311	354	8	3439	
79	283	220	142	157	165	173	181	189	197	205	138	224	113	249	306	56	359	3	3439	
109	253	237	125	196	204	163	164	172	180	188	238	124	96	266	303	59	360	2	3439	
261	101	147	215	179	187	195	203	162	170	171	212	150	243	119	41	321	351	11	3439	
265	97	127	235	169	177	178	186	194	202	161	218	144	276	86	297	65	27	335	3439	
85	277	136	226	201	160	168	176	184	185	193	121	241	290	72	299	63	348	14	3439	
71	291	211	151	191	192	200	159	167	175	183	128	234	69	293	44	318	357	5	3439	
76	286	155	207	174	182	190	198	199	158	166	216	146	279	83	46	316	28	334	3439	
263	99	240	122	239	145	154	143	223	149	133	233	210	91	271	50	312	19	343	3439	
87	275	156	206	123	217	208	219	139	213	229	129	152	278	84	294	68	24	338	3439	
257	105	120	267	107	88	282	111	254	110	73	272	92	292	285	38	324	34	328	3439	
247	115	242	95	255	274	80	251	108	252	289	90	270	70	77	300	62	30	332	3439	
313	325	60	53	54	320	317	319	67	314	52	57	58	323	315	64	66	23	339	3439	
49	37	302	309	308	42	45	43	295	48	310	305	304	39	47	296	298	18	344	3439	
356	361	341	33	29	16	25	36	22	26	32	342	349	358	31	350	352	35	345	3439	
6	1	21	329	333	346	337	326	340	336	330	20	13	4	331	12	10	17	327	3439	
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26	mgc	4015	3419	3064	3477	3313	3113	3631	3413	3176	3610	3753	3475	2754	3900	3436	3648	3465	3240	3439
273	280	117	114	268	264	256	104	100	75	118	281	103	102	260	294	68	354	8	3439	
89	82	245	248	94	98	106	258	262	287	244	81	259	112	250	307	55	360	2	3439	
269	93	178	183	182	187	175	194	168	147	215	139	223	288	74	40	322	353	9	3439	
284	78	185	181	177	188	174	201	161	156	206	230	132	116	246	50	312	348	14	3439	
79	283	180	179	184	170	192	198	164	152	210	133	229	113	249	306	56	359	3	3439	
109	253	176	172	173	191	193	195	167	154	208	240	122	91	271	303	59	355	7	3439	
261	101	186	190	189	169	171	159	203	217	145	235	127	243	119	41	321	351	11	3439	
265	97	196	160	197	200	158	157	199	214	148	131	231	276	86	297	65	27	335	3439	
85	277	166	202	165	162	204	163	205	153	209	135	227	290	72	299	63	347	15	3439	
71	291	218	219	155	149	150	151	221	220	146	236	126	69	293	44	318	357	5	3439	
76	286	144	143	207	213	212	211	141	216	142	140	222	279	83	46	316	28	334	3439	
263	99	232	124	226	123	121	225	129	228	125	234	224	96	266	51	311	19	343	3439	
87	275	130	238	136	239	241	137	233	134	237	138	128	278	84	301	61	24	338	3439	
257	105	120	267	107	88	282	111	254	110	73	272	92	292	285	38	324	34	328	3439	
247	115	242	95	255	274	80	251	108	252	289	90	270	70	77	300	62	30	332	3439	
313	325	60	53	54	320	317	319	67	314	52	57	58	323	315	64	66	23	339	3439	
49	37	302	309	308	42	45	43	295	48	310	305	304	39	47	296	298	18	344	3439	
356	361	341	33	29	16	25	36	22	26	32	342	349	358	31	350	352	35	345	3439	
6	1	21	329	333	346	337	326	340	336	330	20	13	4	331	12	10	17	327	3439	
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27	mgc	4015	3419	3064	3477	3304	3106	3639	3423	3176	3639	3725	3467	2759	3900	3436	3648	3465	3240	3439
273	280	117	114	268	264	256	104	100	75	118	281	103	102	260	294	68	354	8	3439	
89	82	245	248	94	98	106	258	262	287	244	81	259	112	250	307	55	360	2	3439	
269	93	169	175	181	187	193	194	168	147	215	139	223	288	74	40	322	353	9	3439	
284	78	186	192	173	174	180	201	161	156	206	230	132	116	246	50	312	348	14	3439	
79	283	178	179	185	191	172	198	164	152	210	133	229	113	249	306	56	359	3	3439	
109	253	190	171	177	183	184	195	167	154	208	240	122	91	271	303	59	355	7	3439	
261	101	182	188	189	170	176	159	203	217	145	235	127	243	119	41	321	351	11	3439	
265	97	196	160	197	200	158	157	199	214	148	131	231	276	86	297	65	27	335	3439	
85	277	166	202	165	162	204	163	205	153	209	135	227	290	72	299	63	347	15	3439	
71	291	218	219	155	149	150	151	221	220	146	236	126	69	293	44	318	357	5	3439	
76	286	144	143	207	213	212	211	141	216	142	140	222	279	83	46	316	28	334	3439	
263	99	232	124	226	123	121	225	129	228	125	234	224	96	266	51	311	19	343	3439	
87	275	130	238	136	239	241	137	233	134	237	138	128	278	84	301	61	24	338	3439	
257	105	120	267	107	88	282	111	254	110	73	272	92	292	285	38	324	34	328	3439	
247	115	242	95	255	274	80	251	108	252	289	90	270	70	77	300	62	30	332	3439	
313	325	60	53	54	320	317	319	67	314	52	57	58	323	315	64	66	23	339	3439	
49	37	302	309	308	42	45	43	295	48	310	305	304	39	47	296	298	18	344	3439	
356	361	341	33	29	16	25	36	22	26	32	342	349	358	31	350	352	35	345	3439	
6	1	21	329	333	346	337	326	340	336	330	20	13	4	331	12	10	17	327	3439	
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28	mgc	4015	3419	3064	3477	3292	3106	3644	3394	3197	3614	3753	3465	2765	3965	3439	3627	3426	3240	3439
273	280	117	114	268	264	256	104	100	75	118	281	10								

29	mgc	4237	3268	3070	3489	3286	3131	3626	3417	3184	3589	3793	3401	2754	4025	3441	3499	3524	3168	3439
273	280	117	114	268	264	256	104	100	75	118	281	103	102	260	294	68	360	2	3439	
89	82	245	248	94	98	106	258	262	287	244	81	259	112	250	301	61	355	7	3439	
269	93	162	211	170	167	204	172	178	146	219	135	227	288	74	51	311	353	9	3439	
284	78	175	161	207	208	163	212	218	183	142	236	126	113	249	38	324	354	8	3439	
79	283	206	171	166	208	176	159	147	214	182	133	229	116	246	306	56	359	3	3439	
109	253	180	148	215	185	141	217	160	209	174	235	127	69	293	303	59	347	15	3439	
261	101	220	179	144	213	181	149	173	165	205	140	222	243	119	41	321	351	11	3439	
265	97	143	216	184	145	221	177	210	169	164	131	231	276	86	297	65	27	335	3439	
85	277	198	193	152	203	186	154	196	191	156	240	122	290	72	299	63	348	14	3439	
71	291	157	197	189	150	199	194	155	201	187	230	132	91	271	44	318	357	5	3439	
76	286	188	153	202	190	158	195	192	151	200	139	223	279	83	46	316	28	334	3439	
263	99	232	124	129	121	123	225	226	228	125	234	224	96	266	50	312	19	343	3439	
87	275	130	238	233	241	239	137	136	134	237	138	128	278	84	307	55	24	338	3439	
257	105	120	267	110	88	282	111	254	107	73	272	92	292	285	40	322	34	328	3439	
247	115	242	95	252	274	80	251	108	255	289	90	270	70	77	300	62	30	332	3439	
325	320	60	53	54	313	317	319	67	314	52	57	58	323	315	64	66	23	339	3439	
37	42	302	309	308	49	45	43	295	48	310	305	304	39	47	296	298	18	344	3439	
361	356	341	33	29	16	25	36	22	26	32	342	349	358	31	350	352	35	345	3439	
1	6	21	329	333	346	337	326	340	336	330	20	13	4	331	12	10	17	327	3439	
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30	mgc	3908	2745	3392	3467	3348	2947	4487	3010	3570	3831	3448	3171	2853	3695	3182	3709	3439	3700	3439
303	82	40	61	38	68	272	295	298	315	278	299	37	288	41	73	289	347	15	3439	
59	280	322	301	324	294	90	67	64	47	84	63	325	74	321	43	319	357	5	3439	
86	276	178	185	180	193	169	195	167	212	150	135	227	120	242	57	305	353	9	3439	
54	308	183	181	179	192	170	201	161	210	152	132	230	109	253	268	94	354	8	3439	
309	53	182	177	184	172	190	162	200	147	215	235	127	108	254	275	87	359	3	3439	
79	283	176	174	191	175	189	157	205	146	216	236	126	252	110	60	302	360	2	3439	
69	293	186	188	171	173	187	160	202	208	154	131	231	118	244	71	291	351	11	3439	
55	307	158	159	199	196	197	194	164	206	156	239	123	259	103	48	314	27	335	3439	
313	49	204	203	163	166	165	198	168	214	148	130	232	263	99	65	297	348	14	3439	
323	39	217	221	155	151	149	219	153	144	220	240	122	258	104	267	95	355	7	3439	
304	58	145	141	207	211	213	143	209	142	218	139	223	113	249	311	51	28	334	3439	
284	78	138	128	137	238	233	140	237	134	136	241	229	119	243	317	45	19	343	3439	
70	292	224	234	225	124	129	222	125	228	226	133	121	264	98	273	89	24	338	3439	
83	279	248	102	250	251	247	100	255	101	245	106	246	105	97	269	93	34	328	3439	
76	286	114	260	112	111	115	262	107	261	117	256	116	265	257	318	44	30	332	3439	
290	72	96	92	271	282	300	46	50	56	274	52	277	281	285	66	287	23	339	3439	
320	42	266	270	91	80	62	316	312	306	88	310	85	81	77	296	75	18	344	3439	
361	26	341	33	29	356	25	36	22	16	32	342	349	358	31	350	352	35	345	3439	
1	336	21	329	333	6	337	326	340	346	330	20	13	4	331	12	10	17	327	3439	
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31	mgc	3908	2745	3392	3467	3339	2940	4495	3014	3570	3846	3456	3163	2842	3695	3182	3709	3439	3700	3439
303	82	40	61	38	68	272	295	298	315	278	299	37	288	41	73	289	347	15	3439	
59	280	322	301	324	294	90	67	64	47	84	63	325	74	321	43	319	357	5	3439	
86	276	169	175	181	187	193	195	167	212	150	135	227	120	242	57	305	353	9	3439	
54	308	186	192	173	174	180	201	161	210	152	132	230	109	253	268	94	354	8	3439	
309	53	178	179	185	191	172	162	200	147	215	235	127	108	254	275	87	359	3	3439	
79	283	190	171	177	183	184	157	205	146	216	236	126	252	110	60	302	360	2	3439	
69	293	182	188	189	170	176	160	202	208	154	131	231	118	244	71	291	351	11	3439	
55	307	158	159	199	196	197	194	164	206	156	239	123	259	103	48	314	27	335	3439	
313	49	204	203	163	166	165	198	168	214	148	130	232	263	99	65	297	348	14	3439	
323	39	217	221	155	151	149	219	153	144	220	240	122	258	104	267	95	355	7	3439	
304	58	145	141	207	211	213	143	209	142	218	139	223	113	249	311	51	28	334	3439	
284	78	138	128	137	238	233	140	237	134	136	241	229	119	243	317	45	19	343	3439	
70	292	224	234	225	124	129	222	125	228	226	133	121	264	98	273	89	24	338	3439	
83	279	248	102	250	251	247	100	255	101	245	106	246	105	97	269	93	34	328	3439	
76	286	114	260	112	111	115	262	107	261	117	256	116	265	257	318	44	30	332	3439	
290	72	96	92	271	282	300	46	50	56	274	52	277	281	285	66	287	23	339	3439	
320	42	266	270	91	80	62	316	312	306	88	310	85	81	77	296	75	18	344	3439	
361	26	341	33	29	356	25	36	22	16	32	342	349	358	31	350	352	35	345	3439	
1	336	21	329	333	6	337	326	340	346	330	20	13	4	331	12	10	17	327	3439	
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32	mgc	3908	2745	3392	3467	3327	2940	4500	2985	3591	3858	3448	3194	2856	3678	3188	3688	3437	3700	3439
303	82	40	61	38	68	272	295	298	315	278	299	37	288	41	73	289	347	15	3439	
59	280	322	301	324	294	90	67	64	47	84	63	325	74	321	43	319	357	5	3439	
86	276	157	165	173	181	189	197	205	212	150	135	227	120	242	57	305	353	9	3439	
54	308	196	204	163	164	172	180	188	210	152	132	230	109	253	268	94	354	8	3439	
309	53	179	187	195	203	162	170	171	147	215	235	127	108	254	275	87	359	3	3439	
79	283	169	177	178	186	194	202	161	146	216	236	126	252	110	60	302	360	2	3439	
69	293	201	160	168	176	184	185	193	208	154	131	231	118	244	71	291	351	11	3439	
55	307	191	192	200	159	167	175	183	206	156	239	123	259	103	48	314	27	335	3439	
313	49	174																		

33	mgc	3902	2726	3380	3467	3345	2965	4490	3011	3561	3837	3490	3066	2853	3799	3185	3655	3401	3769	3439
303	82	40	61	38	68	272	295	298	315	278	299	37	288	41	73	289	359	3	3439	
59	280	322	301	324	294	90	67	64	47	84	63	325	74	321	43	319	348	14	3439	
86	276	162	211	170	167	204	172	178	146	219	131	231	120	242	71	291	353	9	3439	
54	308	175	161	207	168	163	212	218	183	142	132	230	109	253	268	94	354	8	3439	
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79	283	180	148	215	185	141	217	160	209	174	236	126	252	110	60	302	347	15	3439	
69	293	220	179	144	213	181	149	173	165	205	135	227	118	244	57	305	351	11	3439	
55	307	143	216	184	145	221	177	210	169	164	240	122	259	103	48	314	27	335	3439	
313	49	198	193	152	203	186	154	196	191	156	130	232	263	99	65	297	357	5	3439	
323	39	157	197	189	150	199	194	155	201	187	239	123	258	104	267	95	355	7	3439	
304	58	188	153	202	190	158	195	192	151	200	139	223	113	249	311	51	28	334	3439	
284	78	138	128	137	238	233	140	237	134	136	241	229	119	243	317	45	19	343	3439	
70	292	224	234	225	124	129	222	125	228	226	133	121	264	98	273	89	24	338	3439	
83	279	248	102	250	251	247	100	255	101	245	106	246	105	97	269	93	34	328	3439	
76	286	114	260	112	111	115	262	107	261	117	256	116	265	257	318	44	30	332	3439	
290	72	96	92	271	282	300	46	50	56	274	52	277	281	285	66	287	23	339	3439	
320	42	266	270	91	80	62	316	312	306	88	310	85	81	77	296	75	18	344	3439	
361	16	341	33	29	356	25	36	22	26	32	342	349	358	31	350	352	35	345	3439	
1	346	21	329	333	6	337	326	340	336	330	20	13	4	331	12	10	17	327	3439	
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34	mgc	3202	3201	3219	3708	3700	2858	3807	3560	2589	4263	2950	3963	3108	3401	3436	3805	3439	3693	3439
184	177	182	192	170	204	158	220	142	132	230	100	262	83	279	308	54	360	2	3439	
179	181	183	193	169	167	195	216	146	138	224	248	114	266	96	299	63	355	7	3439	
180	185	178	172	190	165	197	214	148	234	128	103	259	269	93	300	62	353	9	3439	
174	176	191	175	189	202	160	150	212	134	228	98	264	271	91	302	60	354	8	3439	
188	186	171	173	187	163	199	218	144	137	225	246	116	74	288	37	325	359	3	3439	
157	201	196	159	162	198	194	149	213	139	223	253	109	280	82	53	309	347	15	3439	
205	161	166	203	200	168	164	154	208	237	125	99	263	272	90	47	315	351	11	3439	
143	141	209	207	211	215	145	152	206	235	127	243	119	75	287	46	316	27	335	3439	
219	221	153	155	151	147	217	156	210	241	121	257	105	270	92	39	323	348	14	3439	
123	129	232	126	226	229	231	222	227	124	122	244	118	275	87	38	324	357	5	3439	
239	233	130	236	136	133	131	140	135	240	238	108	254	274	88	305	57	28	334	3439	
107	247	106	102	104	101	249	252	97	251	245	242	250	73	289	310	52	19	343	3439	
255	115	256	260	258	261	113	110	265	111	117	112	120	79	283	42	320	24	338	3439	
293	80	94	85	291	89	284	95	81	286	285	290	86	84	292	294	68	34	328	3439	
69	282	268	277	71	273	78	267	281	76	77	72	276	70	278	41	321	30	332	3439	
307	301	40	50	51	298	44	49	306	303	295	304	45	296	48	297	43	23	339	3439	
55	61	322	312	311	64	318	313	56	59	67	58	317	66	314	319	65	18	344	3439	
356	361	341	33	29	16	25	36	22	26	32	342	349	358	31	350	352	35	345	3439	
6	1	21	329	333	346	337	326	340	336	330	20	13	4	331	12	10	17	327	3439	
3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439

35	mgc	3187	3206	3227	3703	3700	2876	3815	3552	2578	4263	2950	3963	3108	3401	3436	3805	3439	3693	3439
169	175	181	187	193	204	158	220	142	132	230	100	262	83	279	308	54	360	2	3439	
186	192	173	174	180	167	195	216	146	138	224	248	114	266	96	299	63	355	7	3439	
178	179	185	191	172	165	197	214	148	234	128	103	259	269	93	300	62	353	9	3439	
190	171	177	183	184	202	160	150	212	134	228	98	264	271	91	302	60	354	8	3439	
182	188	189	170	176	163	199	218	144	137	225	246	116	74	288	37	325	359	3	3439	
157	201	196	159	162	198	194	149	213	139	223	253	109	280	82	53	309	347	15	3439	
205	161	166	203	200	168	164	154	208	237	125	99	263	272	90	47	315	351	11	3439	
143	141	209	207	211	215	145	152	206	235	127	243	119	75	287	46	316	27	335	3439	
219	221	153	155	151	147	217	156	210	241	121	257	105	270	92	39	323	348	14	3439	
123	129	232	126	226	229	231	222	227	124	122	244	118	275	87	38	324	357	5	3439	
239	233	130	236	136	133	131	140	135	240	238	108	254	274	88	305	57	28	334	3439	
107	247	106	102	104	101	249	252	97	251	245	242	250	73	289	310	52	19	343	3439	
255	115	256	260	258	261	113	110	265	111	117	112	120	79	283	42	320	24	338	3439	
293	80	94	85	291	89	284	95	81	286	285	290	86	84	292	294	68	34	328	3439	
69	282	268	277	71	273	78	267	281	76	77	72	276	70	278	41	321	30	332	3439	
307	301	40	50	51	298	44	49	306	303	295	304	45	296	48	297	43	23	339	3439	
55	61	322	312	311	64	318	313	56	59	67	58	317	66	314	319	65	18	344	3439	
356	361	341	33	29	16	25	36	22	26	32	342	349	358	31	350	352	35	345	3439	
6	1	21	329	333	346	337	326	340	336	330	20	13	4	331	12	10	17	327	3439	
3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439

36	mgc	3175	3206	3232	3674	3721	2880	3807	3591	2584	4286	2920	3942	3110	3401	3436	3805	3439	3693	3439
157	165	173	181	189	197	205	220	142	132	230	100	262	83	279	308	54	360	2	3439	
196	204	163	164	172	180	188	216	146	138	224	248	114	266	96	299	63	355	7	3439	
179	187	195	203	162	170	171	214	148	234	128	103	259	269	93	300	62	353	9	3439	
169	177	178	186	194	202	161	150	212	134	228	98	264	271	91	302	60	354	8	3439	
201	160	168	176	184	185	193	218	144	137	225	246	116	74	288	37	325	359	3	3439	
191	192	200	159	167	175	183	149	213	139	223	253	109	280	82	53	309	347	15	3439	
174	182	190	198	199	158	166	154	208	237	125	99	263	272	90	47	315	351	11	3439	
143	141	209	207	211	215	145	152	206	235	127	243	119	75	287	46	316	27	335	3439	
219	221	153	155	151	147	217	156	210	241	121	257	105	270	92	39	323	348	14	3439	

37	mgc	3180	3231	3213	3699	3701	2859	3849	3529	2589	4216	2974	3897	3207	3447	3408	3781	3429	3693	3439
162	211	170	167	204	172	178	146	219	132	230	100	262	83	279	308	54	360	2	3439	
175	161	207	168	163	212	218	183	142	138	224	248	114	266	96	299	63	355	7	3439	
206	171	166	208	176	159	147	214	182	234	128	103	259	269	93	300	62	353	9	3439	
180	148	215	185	141	217	160	209	174	134	228	98	264	271	91	302	60	354	8	3439	
220	179	144	213	181	149	173	165	205	137	225	246	116	74	288	37	325	359	3	3439	
143	216	184	145	221	177	210	169	164	139	223	253	109	280	82	53	309	347	15	3439	
198	193	152	203	186	154	196	191	156	237	125	99	263	272	90	47	315	351	11	3439	
157	197	189	150	199	194	155	201	187	235	127	243	119	75	287	46	316	27	335	3439	
188	153	202	190	158	195	192	151	200	241	121	257	105	270	92	39	323	348	14	3439	
123	129	232	126	226	229	231	222	227	124	122	244	118	275	87	38	324	357	5	3439	
239	233	130	236	136	133	131	140	135	240	238	108	254	274	88	305	57	28	334	3439	
107	247	106	102	104	101	249	252	97	251	245	242	250	73	289	310	52	19	343	3439	
255	115	256	260	258	261	113	110	265	111	117	112	120	79	283	42	320	24	338	3439	
293	80	94	85	291	89	284	95	81	286	285	290	86	84	292	294	68	34	328	3439	
69	282	268	277	71	273	78	267	281	76	77	72	276	70	278	41	321	30	332	3439	
307	301	40	50	51	298	44	49	306	303	295	304	45	296	48	297	43	23	339	3439	
55	61	322	312	311	64	318	313	56	59	67	58	317	66	314	319	65	18	344	3439	
356	361	341	33	29	16	25	36	22	26	32	342	349	358	31	350	352	35	345	3439	
6	1	21	329	333	346	337	326	340	336	330	20	13	4	331	12	10	17	327	3439	
3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439

38	mgc	3036	3090	3564	3553	3362	3359	3426	3550	2792	4426	2979	3812	3108	3698	3086	3791	3381	3889	3439
117	122	260	228	108	256	99	105	230	239	227	115	247	83	279	302	60	351	11	3439	
245	240	102	134	254	106	263	257	132	123	135	232	130	74	288	299	63	348	14	3439	
140	222	211	215	165	143	150	217	166	204	158	243	119	269	93	294	68	360	2	3439	
249	113	151	147	197	219	212	145	196	200	162	223	139	271	91	310	52	354	8	3439	
262	100	141	221	172	188	183	180	182	149	213	235	127	266	96	37	325	353	9	3439	
242	120	153	209	190	174	179	193	169	195	167	125	237	280	82	53	309	355	7	3439	
109	253	208	154	184	178	181	170	192	142	220	129	233	272	90	47	315	359	3	3439	
98	264	205	157	186	176	177	191	175	161	201	101	261	75	287	46	316	27	335	3439	
121	241	152	210	173	189	185	171	187	216	146	114	248	270	92	39	323	347	15	3439	
112	250	202	160	194	163	155	164	159	218	214	238	124	275	87	38	324	357	5	3439	
265	97	206	156	168	199	207	198	203	144	148	236	126	274	88	305	57	28	334	3439	
255	107	258	110	225	259	251	131	116	136	244	133	128	73	289	308	54	19	343	3439	
138	224	104	252	137	103	111	231	246	226	118	229	234	79	283	42	320	24	338	3439	
293	80	94	85	284	95	291	89	81	286	285	290	86	84	292	300	62	34	328	3439	
69	282	268	277	78	267	71	273	281	76	77	72	276	70	278	41	321	30	332	3439	
307	301	40	306	51	298	44	49	50	303	295	304	45	296	48	297	43	23	339	3439	
55	61	322	56	311	64	318	313	56	59	67	58	317	66	314	319	65	18	344	3439	
341	361	356	33	29	16	25	36	22	26	32	342	349	358	31	350	352	35	345	3439	
21	1	6	329	333	346	337	326	340	336	330	20	13	4	331	12	10	17	327	3439	
3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439

39	mgc	2996	3151	3564	3553	3314	3378	3510	3561	2740	4340	3109	3706	3108	3799	3022	3874	3350	3827	3439
117	122	260	228	108	256	99	105	230	239	227	115	247	83	279	302	60	348	14	3439	
245	240	102	134	254	106	263	257	132	123	135	232	130	74	288	299	63	359	3	3439	
140	222	162	211	170	167	204	172	160	209	174	243	119	269	93	294	68	351	11	3439	
249	113	175	161	207	168	163	212	173	165	205	223	139	271	91	310	52	354	8	3439	
262	100	206	171	166	208	176	159	210	169	164	235	127	266	96	37	325	353	9	3439	
242	120	180	148	215	185	141	217	178	146	219	129	233	280	82	53	309	355	7	3439	
109	253	220	179	144	213	181	149	218	183	142	125	237	272	90	47	315	360	2	3439	
98	264	143	216	184	145	221	177	147	214	182	101	261	75	287	46	316	27	335	3439	
121	241	198	193	152	203	186	154	196	191	156	114	248	270	92	39	323	347	15	3439	
112	250	157	197	189	150	199	194	155	201	187	238	124	275	87	38	324	357	5	3439	
265	97	188	153	202	190	158	195	192	151	200	236	126	274	88	305	57	28	334	3439	
255	107	258	110	225	259	251	131	116	136	244	133	128	73	289	308	54	19	343	3439	
138	224	104	252	137	103	111	231	246	226	118	229	234	79	283	42	320	24	338	3439	
293	80	94	85	284	95	291	89	81	286	285	290	86	84	292	300	62	34	328	3439	
69	282	268	277	78	267	71	273	281	76	77	72	276	70	278	41	321	30	332	3439	
307	301	40	306	51	298	44	49	50	303	295	304	45	296	48	297	43	23	339	3439	
55	61	322	56	311	64	318	313	56	59	67	58	317	66	314	319	65	18	344	3439	
341	361	356	33	29	16	25	36	22	26	32	342	349	358	31	350	352	35	345	3439	
21	1	6	329	333	346	337	326	340	336	330	20	13	4	331	12	10	17	327	3439	
3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439

40	mgc	2991	3115	3576	3546	3330	3360	3516	3544	2737	4365	3086	3675	3144	3694	3151	3926	3280	3866	3439
117	122	260	228	108	256	99	105	230	239	227	115	247	83	279	302	60	348	14	3439	
245	240	102	134	254	106	263	257	132	123	135	232	130	74	288	299	63	359	3	3439	
140	222	178	183	182	174	188	163	199	207	155	125	237	269	93	294	68	351	11	3439	
249	113	185	181	177	175	187	198	164	145	217	223	139	271	91	308	54	354	8	3439	
262	100	180	179	184	192	170	159	203	144	218	235	127	266	96	37	325	353	9	3439	
242	120	176	172	173	193	191	158	204	212	150	129	233	280	82	53	309	355	7	3439	
109	253	186	190	189	171	169	195	167	209	153	243	119	272	90	47	315	360	2	3439	
98	264	201	157	160	196	197	194	162	149	213	114	248	75	287	46	316	27	335	3439	
121																				

41	mgc	2991	3115	3576	3546	3324	3370	3514	3561	2737	4328	3102	3659	3162	3694	3151	3926	3280	3866	3439	42	mgc	2991	3115	3576	3546	3309	3353	3529	3538	2758	4360	3086	3735	3122	3643	3192	3905	3278	3866	3439
117	122	260	228	108	256	99	105	230	239	227	115	247	83	279	302	60	348	14	3439	117	122	260	228	108	256	99	105	230	239	227	115	247	83	279	302	60	348	14	3439		
245	240	102	134	254	106	263	257	132	123	135	232	130	74	288	299	63	359	3	3439	245	240	102	134	254	106	263	257	132	123	135	232	130	74	288	299	63	359	3	3439		
140	222	172	188	183	180	182	163	199	207	155	125	237	269	93	294	68	351	11	3439	140	222	157	165	173	181	189	197	205	207	155	125	237	269	93	294	68	351	11	3439		
249	113	190	174	179	193	169	198	164	145	217	223	139	271	91	308	54	354	8	3439	249	113	196	204	163	164	172	180	188	145	217	223	139	271	91	308	54	354	8	3439		
262	100	184	178	181	170	192	159	203	144	218	235	127	266	96	37	325	353	9	3439	262	100	179	187	195	203	162	170	171	144	218	235	127	266	96	37	325	353	9	3439		
242	120	186	176	177	191	175	158	204	212	150	129	233	280	82	53	309	355	7	3439	242	120	169	177	178	186	194	202	161	212	150	129	233	280	82	53	309	355	7	3439		
109	253	173	189	185	171	187	195	167	209	153	243	119	272	90	47	315	360	2	3439	109	253	201	160	168	176	184	185	193	209	153	243	119	272	90	47	315	360	2	3439		
98	264	201	157	160	196	197	194	162	149	213	114	248	75	287	46	316	27	335	3439	98	264	191	192	200	159	167	175	183	149	213	114	248	75	287	46	316	27	335	3439		
121	241	161	205	202	166	165	200	168	143	219	101	261	270	92	39	323	347	15	3439	121	241	174	182	190	198	199	158	166	143	219	101	261	270	92	39	323	347	15	3439		
112	250	141	216	211	147	208	210	142	206	148	238	124	275	87	38	324	357	5	3439	112	250	141	216	211	147	208	210	142	206	148	238	124	275	87	38	324	357	5	3439		
265	97	221	146	151	215	154	152	220	214	156	236	126	274	88	305	57	28	334	3439	265	97	221	146	151	215	154	152	220	214	156	236	126	274	88	305	57	28	334	3439		
255	107	258	110	225	259	244	136	116	131	251	133	128	73	289	310	52	19	343	3439	255	107	258	110	225	259	244	136	116	131	251	133	128	73	289	310	52	19	343	3439		
138	224	104	252	137	103	118	226	246	231	111	229	234	79	283	42	320	24	338	3439	138	224	104	252	137	103	118	226	246	231	111	229	234	79	283	42	320	24	338	3439		
293	80	94	85	284	95	291	89	81	286	285	290	86	84	292	300	62	34	328	3439	293	80	94	85	284	95	291	89	81	286	285	290	86	84	292	300	62	34	328	3439		
69	282	268	277	78	267	71	273	281	76	77	72	276	70	278	41	321	30	332	3439	69	282	268	277	78	267	71	273	281	76	77	72	276	70	278	41	321	30	332	3439		
307	301	40	306	51	298	44	49	50	303	295	304	45	296	48	297	43	23	339	3439	307	301	40	306	51	298	44	49	50	303	295	304	45	296	48	297	43	23	339	3439		
55	61	322	56	311	64	318	313	312	59	67	58	317	66	314	319	65	18	344	3439	55	61	322	56	311	64	318	313	312	59	67	58	317	66	314	319	65	18	344	3439		
342	361	356	33	29	16	25	36	22	26	32	341	349	358	31	350	352	35	345	3439	342	361	356	33	29	16	25	36	22	26	32	341	349	358	31	350	352	35	345	3439		
20	1	6	329	333	346	337	326	340	336	330	21	13	4	331	12	10	17	327	3439	20	1	6	329	333	346	337	326	340	336	330	21	13	4	331	12	10	17	327	3439		
3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	

More examples of magic squares of order 19 are given in author's work [71].

2.1 Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 133 and 114

Let's consider **bordered** magic square of orders 6 and 7 given by

6x6							111
	6	30	3	36	4	32	111
	35	17	22	11	24	2	111
	29	12	23	18	21	8	111
	27	26	13	20	15	10	111
	9	19	16	25	14	28	111
	5	7	34	1	33	31	111
	111	111	111	111	111	111	111

7x7								175
	42	38	40	5	4	2	44	175
	1	34	37	17	19	18	49	175
	3	14	24	29	22	36	47	175
	43	15	23	25	27	35	7	175
	41	30	28	21	26	20	9	175
	39	32	13	33	31	16	11	175
	6	12	10	45	46	48	8	175
	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175

The entries of above two magic squares are sequential numbers starting from 1:

$$D_{6 \times 6} := \{1, 2, \dots, 35, 36\}$$

$$D_{7 \times 7} := \{1, 2, \dots, 48, 49\}$$

The property of **bordered** magic squares is that removing the upper borders still we are left with magic squares of sequential values.

Multiplying each entry of above two magic squares of orders 6 and 7 by 361, we get

6x6							40071
	2166	10830	1083	12996	1444	11552	40071
	12635	6137	7942	3971	8664	722	40071
	10469	4332	8303	6498	7581	2888	40071
	9747	9386	4693	7220	5415	3610	40071
	3249	6859	5776	9025	5054	10108	40071
	1805	2527	12274	361	11913	11191	40071
	40071	40071	40071	40071	40071	40071	40071

7x7								63175
	15162	13718	14440	1805	1444	722	15884	63175
	361	12274	13357	6137	6859	6498	17689	63175
	1083	5054	8664	10469	7942	12996	16967	63175
	15523	5415	8303	9025	9747	12635	2527	63175
	14801	10830	10108	7581	9386	7220	3249	63175
	14079	11552	4693	11913	11191	5776	3971	63175
	2166	4332	3610	16245	16606	17328	2888	63175
	63175	63175	63175	63175	63175	63175	63175	63175

In this case, the entries distributions of these two magic squares are given by

$$D_{7 \times 7} := \{361, 722, \dots, 12635, 12996\}$$

$$D_{8 \times 8} := \{361, 722, \dots, 17328, 17689\}$$

Let's replace entries of above two magic squares by magic squares of order 17. In each case, the entries chosen are as given below:

$$361 \rightarrow 1, 2, \dots, 361$$

$$722 \rightarrow 362, 363, \dots, 722$$

$$1083 \rightarrow 723, 724, \dots, 1083$$

$$\dots \rightarrow \dots \dots$$

$$\dots \rightarrow \dots \dots$$

This lead us to two big **bordered** magic squares of orders 133 and 114 multiples of 19. Since these two magic squares

are very big, these are given in **excel files** attached with this work. There are total 42 magic squares of orders 133 and 114 multiples of order 19.

Due to bigger size of magic squares, below are only three examples of magic squares of order 57 multiples of order 19

2.2 Magic Squares of Order 57

Below are three examples of magic squares of order 57 obtained from magic squares of order 133. It is obtained by the application of the formula $\frac{a^2 - b^2}{2}$, $a > b$, i.e., subtract $\frac{114^2 - 57^2}{2} := 7220$ from each entry of magic square order 133. Removing the external borders, we are left with following magic squares of order 57:

Table of Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 19, Zenodo. The table contains 31 rows and 31 columns of numerical data, with a header row and column labeled 'mgc' and '3'. The numbers range from 1 to 92625.

Table of Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 19, containing numerical data in a grid format with columns labeled by row and column indices (e.g., 12, 1404, 1107, etc.).

35	mgc	92498	94588	96072	97701	99427	101216	103316	105486	107724	110031	112400	114830	117321	119874	122490	125169	127902	130691	133536	136437	139394	142407	145476	148601	151782	155019	158312	161661	165066	168527	172044	175613	179234	182907	186632	190409	194238	198119	202052	206039	210080	214175	218324	222527	226784	231095	235460	239879	244352	248880	253461	258096	262787	267534	272337	277196	282111	287082	292109	297192	302331	307524	312771	318022	323377	328736	334199	339668	345143	350624	356115	361616	367127	372648	378179	383720	389271	394832	400403	405984	411575	417176	422787	428408	434039	439680	445331	450992	456663	462344	468035	473736	479447	485168	490899	496640	502391	508152	513923	519704	525495	531296	537107	542928	548759	554590	560431	566282	572143	578014	583895	589786	595687	601598	607519	613450	619391	625342	631293	637254	643225	649196	655177	661168	667169	673180	679191	685212	691243	697284	703335	709396	715467	721548	727639	733740	739851	745972	752103	758244	764395	770556	776727	782908	789099	795300	801511	807732	813963	820204	826455	832716	838987	845268	851559	857860	864171	870492	876823	883164	889515	895876	902247	908628	915019	921420	927831	934252	940683	947124	953575	960036	966507	972988	979479	985980	992491	999012	1004543	1010074	1015615	1021166	1026727	1032298	1037879	1043470	1049071	1054682	1060303	1065934	1071575	1077226	1082887	1088558	1094239	1099930	1105631	1111342	1117063	1122794	1128535	1134286	1140047	1145818	1151599	1157390	1163191	1169002	1174823	1180654	1186495	1192346	1198207	1204078	1209959	1215850	1221751	1227662	1233583	1239514	1245455	1251406	1257367	1263338	1269319	1275310	1281311	1287322	1293343	1299374	1305415	1311466	1317527	1323598	1329679	1335770	1341871	1347982	1354103	1360234	1366375	1372526	1378687	1384858	1391039	1397230	1403431	1410042	1416663	1423294	1429935	1436586	1443247	1449918	1456599	1463290	1470001	1476722	1483463	1490224	1496995	1503776	1510567	1517368	1524179	1530990	1537811	1544642	1551483	1558334	1565195	1572066	1578947	1585838	1592739	1599650	1606571	1613502	1620443	1627394	1634355	1641326	1648307	1655298	1662299	1669310	1676331	1683362	1690403	1697454	1704515	1711586	1718667	1725758	1732859	1739970	1747091	1754222	1761363	1768514	1775675	1782846	1790027	1797218	1804419	1811630	1818851	1826082	1833323	1840574	1847835	1855106	1862387	1869678	1876979	1884290	1891611	1898942	1906283	1913634	1921005	1928386	1935777	1943178	1950589	1958010	1965441	1972882	1980333	1987794	1995265	2002746	2010237	2017738	2025249	2032770	2040291	2047822	2055363	2062914	2070475	2078046	2085627	2093218	2100819	2108430	2116051	2123682	2131323	2138974	2146635	2154306	2161987	2169678	2177379	2185090	2192811	2200542	2208283	2216034	2223795	2231566	2239347	2247138	2254939	2262750	2270571	2278402	2286243	2294094	2301955	2309826	2317707	2325598	2333509	2341430	2349361	2357302	2365253	2373214	2381185	2389166	2397157	2405158	2413169	2421190	2429221	2437262	2445313	2453374	2461445	2469526	2477617	2485718	2493829	2501950	2510081	2518222	2526373	2534534	2542705	2550886	2559077	2567278	2575489	2583710	2591941	2600182	2608433	2616694	2624965	2633246	2641537	2649838	2658149	2666470	2674801	2683142	2691493	2700054	2708625	2717206	2725797	2734408	2743029	2751660	2760301	2768952	2777613	2786284	2794965	2803666	2812377	2821098	2829829	2838570	2847321	2856082	2864853	2873634	2882425	2891226	2900037	2908858	2917689	2926530	2935381	2944242	2953113	2962004	2970905	2979816	2988737	2997668	3006609	3015560	3024521	3033492	3042473	3051464	3060465	3069476	3078497	3087528	3096569	3105620	3114681	3123752	3132833	3141924	3151025	3160136	3169257	3178388	3187529	3196680	3205841	3215012	3224193	3233384	3242585	3251796	3261017	3270248	3279489	3288740	3297991	3307252	3316523	3325804	3335095	3344396	3353707	3363028	3372359	3381690	3391031	3400382	3409743	3419114	3428495	3437886	3447287	3456698	3466119	3475550	3485001	3494462	3503933	3513414	3522905	3532406	3541917	3551438	3560969	3570510	3580061	3589622	3599193	3608774	3618365	3627966	3637577	3647198	3656829	3666470	3676121	3685782	3695453	3705134	3714825	3724526	3734237	3743948	3753669	3763390	3773121	3782862	3792613	3802374	3812145	3821926	3831717	3841518	3851329	3861150	3870981	3880822	3890673	3900534	3910405	3920286	3930177	3940078	3949989	3959910	3969841	3979782	3989733	3999694	4009665	4019646	4029637	4039638	4049649	4059670	4069701	4079742	4089793	4099854	4109925	4119996	4129977	4139968	4149969	4159980	4169991	4179992	4189993	4199994	4209995	4219996	4229997	4239998	4249999	4259999	4269999	4279999	4289999	4299999	4309999	4319999	4329999	4339999	4349999	4359999	4369999	4379999	4389999	4399999	4409999	4419999	4429999	4439999	4449999	4459999	4469999	4479999	4489999	4499999	4509999	4519999	4529999	4539999	4549999	4559999	4569999	4579999	4589999	4599999	4609999	4619999	4629999	4639999	4649999	4659999	4669999	4679999	4689999	4699999	4709999	4719999	4729999	4739999	4749999	4759999	4769999	4779999	4789999	4799999	4809999	4819999	4829999	4839999	4849999	4859999	4869999	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Above there are only three examples of magic square of order 57 multiples of 19. The other examples are given in an **excel files** attached with the work.

Remark 1. Since the magic squares of order 76 are very big to put here in the work, but they are calculated with the same process of order 57. We used magic square of order 114 instead of magic square of order 133.

3 Author's Contribution to Recreation of Numbers and Magic Squares

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers - <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=671>.
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